

THE DEVELOPMENT, CURRENT SITUATIONS AND CHALLENGES OF MONGOLIAN JOURNALISM

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Abstract

Journalism in Mongolia has been understudied at the level of international researchers and has remained largely unnoticed. Mongolian journalism studies are usually published in Mongolian or in local academic circles, which may have limited access to the international academic community. This article focuses on how journalism in Mongolia has evolved over 110 years, as well as the current situation and the challenges. The Mongolian media industry began with the first newspaper called "Shine Toli Hemeeh Bichig" in 1913. Currently, the industry has grown to fully operational 451 media outlets. The foundation for autonomous and independent media was established when Mongolia transitioned to a new political and economic system and gained publishing freedom in 1990. This article briefly summarizes Mongolian journalism's history and mentions the media's legal environment, the characteristics of Mongolian national journalism, the current situation, future development trends and troubles. There are challenges with improving the legal environment, forming ethical journalists, clarifying relations with government agencies and the media and introducing new technologies in the digital era.

Keywords: Mongolian journalism, press freedom, censorship, free press, media management, social media

INTRODUCTION

In the international academic community, Mongolia's journalism industry is rarely known or paid attention to and remained poorly studied by the international journalism studies. For the first time, this article introduces the history and latest developments of Mongolia's journalism industry in depth and systematically to the international academic community.

Mongolia is located in central Asia with estimated population of 3.4 million people and over 450 media outlets. Ever since the early 1990 when transformed into liberal democracy, country has highly valued the freedom of rights, freedom of media. Freedom of speech, expression, and rights to information has guaranteed with Mongolian law. Even with that there is a limitation in freedom of media and censorship.

The history of Mongolian national journalism has been deeply connected with the history of modern Mongolia. Journalism was essential in the 1911 National Revolution, 1921 the People's Revolution, and the 1990-Democratic Revolution. Mongolian journalism in the period up to 1990 can be described as communist, socialist-era journalism, and ideological journalism and was called jointly Soviet-Style journalism. (Odmandakh.M, 2021) After Mongolia transitioned into a democratic and free society in 1990, the government prohibited media censorship and established the concept of independent media and a "free press." Since the 1990s, Public relations has been given the chance and liberty to honestly act as a human social environment, free from political ideology (Bold-Erdene.B, 2006) demand, and interest.

Independent and free media and journalism are growing in Mongolia, with 451 media outlets operating in the country. Since the early 2000s, Mongolia has been experiencing a boom in information technology and the evolution of digital media. News websites and

social media platforms such as Facebook and X (formerly Twitter) have become Mongolians' main information and communication sources. It is essential to strengthen the journalism field, transition to professional, independent, independent and ethical journalism, and create new trends and methods. This journalism history backgrounds and challenges as an ideal subjects for this study. It is important to study the historical development and current status of Mongolian journalism depending on the history of Mongolia in the last century, starting from 1913 to date. Mongolian Press freedom has generally improved, but challenges still persist. Traditional nomadic culture influences media consumption habits, with a growing presence of online and social media.

Literature review

The study of the development of journalism in Mongolia is based on the historical analysis of the periods of the emergence of periodicals in Mongolia, the emergence of journalism, the period of The Bogd Khanate of Mongolia, and socialism. (B.Galaarid, 2018) The foundation of the Mongolian mass media system was laid in 1913 by the newspaper ("Shine toli hemeeh bichig,") which was formed in the 70s with the advent of Mongolian television. (M.Zulkafil, 1997) Over the past 110 years, Mongolian journalism has had three significant achievements. The first is establishing and strengthening the media system, the second is the maturity of the full range of journalistic treatises, and the third is professional journalists. The Mongolian media landscape might be seen as volatile, with so many new outlets launched every year and just as many closed. The media landscape is going through some dramatic changes. On the other hand, some of the major trends are relatively stable both within the press and the electronic media. (M.Munkhmandakh, 2001).

Today, Mongolian journalism is approaching the standard of advanced journalism and substantially impacts social and political life. (zms, 2023) Journalism training and research in Mongolia began in the mid-sixties of the last century. D.Geleg's three-volume history of Mongolian printing became the starting point for this work. Since then, more than 400 books on journalism theory, history and methodology have been published, and sixty scholars have studied them. (newspaper, 2023).

G.Deleg, L.Norovsuren, M.Zulkafil researchers and journalists have published monographs and other books, articles and papers. The council for doctoral studies in journalism was reformed, and L. Norovsuren, B.Bold-Erdene, Ch.Chisamba, S. Batmunkh, G.Unurbayar, D.Dagiimaa, T.Oyunbileg, Ch. Bazar, T. Batzorig, D.Sandagsuren, M. Naranchimeg, B.Gaalaarid, B.Chinzorig are the discussion and defense of the work of more than a dozen researchers who have accelerated the development of modern Mongolian journalism. (sonin.mn, 2021)

The training of journalists with higher education in Mongolia began in the 1960s. In 1995, the establishment of a specialized Council for doctoral studies in journalism under the Department of Journalism and Mass Communication of the National University of Mongolia is considered to have contributed to the preparation of journalists at the doctoral level and the deepening of journalistic research. Scholars have examined aspects of journalism history, theory, challenges, and development trends.

It is impossible to improve the quality, competency of journalist, efficiency, and capacity of journalism without critics, feedback, research, development of journalism theory, and assessment on journalist produce. (M.Zulkafil, Mass media and Journalism in Modern Mongolia, 2007)

There is a need for development of journalism critic association, centralized research from the many researcher to in-depth research in journalism, and projects on priority topics with associated organizations.

The International Conference (Mongolia N. U., 2023) was held in Ulaanbaatar in 2023, March cooperation with the Department of Journalism and Mass Communication of the University of Mongolia and Independent Authority Against Corruption of Mongolia. The discussion of the current media environment was a first major step in bringing international scholars together to determine the current state of journalism and allowing researchers to pay attention to Mongolian journalism.

However, at the research and analysis level, it is still necessary to examine the current situation and to identify the challenges, as well as more recent data and research on Mongolian journalism.

Research objectives and questions

This article's objective is to examine the history of journalism, the current situation and challenges in Mongolia. We therefore, first of all, we aim to outline the history of Mongolian journalism, analyze the current situation, study the legal regulation of the media, identify challenges, and identify future trends. We

specifically seek to answer the following research questions:

- How has journalism in Mongolia evolved over time?
- What are the key characteristics of the current state of Mongolian journalism, including its legal framework?
- What are the major challenges faced by Mongolian journalism today?
- How does the digital revolution and the rise of social media platforms impact journalism in Mongolia?

Methods

The article seeks to define the problem from the perspective of dialectical materialism and historical materialism by collecting, describing, analyzing, and comparing the processes of developing events from existing data and integrating the latest data. Used inductive and comparative analysis methods to explore the challenges of Mongolian journalism development.

The method that the researchers use in this study is data analysis, including general and special scientific cognitive methods, research methods in the literature, historiography, systematization, modeling, comparison, logic, and other research methods. In addition to previous scientists' theses and scientific articles, the Mongolian Press Institute's research, Maxima Consulting LLC's reports, media ownership reports, and internet-based digital data such as the number of internet users and the number of registered Mongolian users on social networks have been used.

HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF JOURNALISM IN MONGOLIA

The development of periodicals in Mongolia

Mongolian journalism's development begins with the history of the regular press. It is believed that the history of Mongolian national journalism started on March 6, 1913, when the newspaper "Shine toli hemeeh bichig" was published. The newspaper published 20 issues in one year and six months. The following newspaper was "Newspaper of the Capital Region," which was printed in a six-page edition on September 1, 1915 and the 103rd issue was published on January 23, 1920. After that, Mongolia's "Unen" newspaper was published for the first time in the Soviet Union (now Irkutsk) on November 10, 1920. The newspaper made its contribution to the process of the 1921 revolution, revealing the feudal rule in Mongolia and its nature, opposing the aggressive activities of foreign countries, Mongolia's foreign affairs, the October Socialist Revolution, and how the people could gain their freedom and create a new government. It served as an essential tool for explaining the nature of the government from many angles, recruiting the People's Regular Army, preparing for armed struggle, promoting the policies and goals of the Mongolian People's Party, and organizing the revolution. In 1922, the Government of the Mongolian People's Republic placed the Press Committee under the control of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and put the entire issue of book publishing under control.

Today, the newspaper is still the media outlet of the Mongolian People's Party, has grown into a regular

publication and is the longest-running weekly in Mongolia. It is followed by daily newspapers such as *Uria*, *People's Rights*, *Truth of Youth*, *Truth of Pioneers*, *Labor*, *Red Star*, *Government News*, *Democracy*, *Ug*, *Today*, *Daily Newspaper*, *Century News*, *National Post*, *Mongolian News*, *Morning Newspaper*, *Zindaa*, *People* and weekly private and free newspapers such as *Business Times*.

The process of transitioning from Soviet-style journalism to "New Era" free and democratic journalism was not so easy. During the "transition" period, the beginning of a free press was established, and the tabloid press was gaining ground.

Mongolian first news agency: Montsame

The National Information Agency MONTSAME is the oldest information organization continuously operating since its establishment in 1921 under the name MONTA or Mongolian Telegraph. Montsame is currently the largest news agency in Mongolia. The MONTSAME Agency first had a complete internet access in 1997 and launched its website to offer daily news contents in Mongolian, Russian and English languages to the global audiences. In 2014, a new website full of contents in Mongolian, English, Chinese, Russian and Japanese was put into effect. This step of MONTSAME to move forward with the global media progressions is the first ever online news channel in various languages in Mongolia. The English and Russian versions of the website montsame.mn/en and montsame.mn/ru are presented by the English and Russian Publications Departments respectively. Also, the Chinese language montsame.mn/cn and Japanese language montsame.mn/jp are delivered by 'Menggu Xiao xi bao' and 'Mongoru Tsushin' newspaper desks. Also, the Agency is widely utilizing different types of channels, such as social media platforms Facebook, X (formerly Twitter) and Youtube with a view of distributing multimedia news stories with photos, audio, video, clips and texts and reach out to the public.

MONTSAME agency is the most significant news network agency with permanent correspondents in Ulaanbaatar, the capital of Mongolia, 21 provinces, Moscow, Russia, and Beijing, China. (Montsame, 2023) The Government of Mongolia meeting on December 31, 2021 decided to transfer the MONTSAME agency to the Office of the President of Mongolia. However, since adopting the Law on Freedom of Media, the agency's legal status has been unclear, and its exact status has been vague.

The agency provides the country's internal affairs news to the government, central institutions, mass media and the general public of Mongolia. The main objective of its work is to inform and promote Mongolia's

foreign and domestic policies, domestic events, and the country's development abroad.

Radio establishment in Mongolia

The first radio station, "Mongolian Radio" was established in 1934 and started operation in Ulaanbaatar, the capital of Mongolia. From the 1950s onwards, Mongolia established a vast radio broadcasting station network. The radio has played an important role in Mongolian social life and has been a reliable source of information. The Soviet Union assisted in training the first radio specialists in the country. Mongolian radio was a state-owned media outlet that carried out party and state propaganda. Although Mongolia has a vast territory, it has a small population. Nomadic herders are far from urban centers and live on the move for four seasons, so radio was the primary means of information dissemination and reception. Since its inception, the Mongolian National Radio has been largest radio station in Mongolia, distributing its articles and programs nationwide. However, since the transition to democracy, privately owned short-wave radios have sprung up.

Development of television

Mongolian National Television was established based on the installed capacity and human resources of Mongolian Radio and in 1967, a vast television network covering the entire country of Mongolia was established. The first specialists were trained in the Soviet Union. Color television appeared in Mongolia in the 1970s. In the 1990s, the media market was liberalized and the first private TV stations, Ulaanbaatar TV, Channel 25, and Channel 5 were established. Furthermore, the first foreign-invested media outlet was founded in 1996 by the US-invested Eagle TV. The TV station was temporarily closed in 2003 and resumed broadcasting in 2005. It is now 100% a subsidiary of the Mongolian company.

Private television stations have also started to be established in local areas, and each of Mongolia's 21 provinces has a television channel. In some areas with a large population and well-developed infrastructure, up to seven television stations operate. For example, there are 7 TV channels in Orkhon Province, 3 in Darkhan-Uul Province, 3 in Hovd and 3 in Umnogov, delivering news and programs for local audiences. In recent years, television channels have diversified into breaking news, sports, children's, educational and entertainment media. In the 2020 Television Viewing Research Report of Maxima Consulting Company, the television stations with the most viewers in Mongolia have been ranked.

Table 1.

Mongolian TOP 10 Television channels

Mongolian TOP 10 TV channels:		
1.	Movie Box	movie
2.	Dream TV	cartoon
3.	MNB	broadcast
4.	Asian box	movie
5.	EDU TV	education & entertainment
6.	TV9	broadcast
7.	NTV	broadcast
8.	Mongol TV	broadcast
9.	MN25	broadcast
10.	UBS	broadcast

Source: Television Viewing Research Report 2020, Maxima Consulting Company

Traditional media changes to New media

The active development of online media began in Mongolia in the early 2000s. News websites and social networks such as Facebook and X (formerly Twitter) have started to appear in Mongolia. Currently, there are many online media platforms, such as websites, social networks, blogs and podcasts, operating in Mongolia.

Most online media platforms broadcast in Mongolian, but some platforms broadcast in English, Russian, Chinese, and other languages.

A 2021 survey by cross-research firm MMCG named the following news websites as the most visited news sites:

Table 2.

Mongolian TOP 10 news websites

Mongolian TOP 10 news websites			
1	Ikon agency	www.ikon.mn	News and political commentary
2	Mongol content company	www.gogo.mn	Expansive coverage
3	Zarig agency	www.zarig.mn	News and political commentary
4	Eagle agency	www.eagle.mn	Breaking news stories
5	Medee agency	www.medee.mn	Breaking news
6	News agency	www.news.mn	News and political commentary
7	Mass agency	www.mass.mn	TV/online, Breaking news
8	Eguur agency	www.eguur.mn	In-depth commentary
9	Paparatsi agency	www.paparatsi.mn	Yellow news
10	Dorgio agency	www.dorgio.mn	Breaking news

Source: National media and Lifestyle report 2021, MMCG

Social media heavily influence Mongolian online media and has become the primary source of information and communication for most of its citizens. In addition, the Government of Mongolia and the Parliament, the highest body of state authority, have opened their social media accounts and are providing news and information. Recently, YouTube podcasts and various reels have become increasingly popular.

Press freedom and legal framework

In a democratic society, the primary condition to prevent the government from arbitrarily restricting and violating fundamental human rights and freedoms is a legal guarantee. Freedom of belief, freedom of expression and freedom of publication are reflected in the Constitution of Mongolia (1992). The right to freedom of expression is closely connected to the release of the press. In 1998, the Parliament of Mongolia approved the Law on Freedom of the Press. This law is the first in the history of Mongolian journalism and the primary rule that guarantees the freedom of the press. The law includes the adoption of laws restricting the freedom of the media and prohibiting the government from controlling or censoring the content of mass media, requiring the media to be responsible for what they publish, and legally preventing the government from taking media under its control (Delgerjargal.M, 2015). The Law

on Public Radio and Television (2005) has been a significant reform in the field of journalism since the enactment of the Freedom of Media Act. This law made the National Radio and Mongolian Television public entities from state-owned entities.

Additionally, in 2011, the Law on Transparency of Information and the Right to Information was approved and this law ensured the transparency of government activities and the right of citizens to seek and receive information. The media industry became one of the three primary industries of strategic importance in Mongolia by the "Law on the Regulation of Foreign Investment" (2012). Because of this law, foreign investment in the media industry is restricted and it became a matter of national security.

The Law on Broadcasting received approval from Parliament in 2019 and it took effect immediately in 2020. This law defines the legal basis of broadcasting services, creates a favorable market environment for fair competition and regulates relations related to broadcasting services that meet national and public interests. And provided for support through the fund. However, the Association of Commercial Televisions considers the distribution of this fund a law that stifles the rights of fair competition, viewers and listeners and is appealing to the Supreme Court to repeal it.

Chart 1. Press Freedom Index Mongolia

Source: <https://rsf.org/en/country/mongolia>

“Reporters without borders” international organization have warned that freedom of the press is inadequate in Mongolia. In 2023, Mongolia ranked 88th out of 180 countries in the Press Freedom Index. Since 2013, the press freedom situation has been evaluated. For example, 98th in 2013, 88th in 2014, 54th in 2015, 60th in 2016, 69th in 2017, 71st in 2018, 70th in 2019, 71st in 2020, 68th in 2021, 90th in 2022 and 88th in 2023. For the press freedom situation to be in the “good enough” category, Mongolia is faced with an urgent need to protect media freedom on a broad scale effectively.

According to the Law on the Procedures of the Sessions of the Parliament of Mongolia 2020, the Speaker of the Parliament will approve the procedures related to the media and public relations, and the law on the Courts of Mongolia 2021 states that the General Council will approve the procedures for informing the public of court decisions. Journalists are reporting to the people within the framework of approved methods. However, the process of providing information to the public in most government agencies is vague, and in some cases, there is a refusal to provide information. The National Security Concept of Mongolia (2010) mentioned that the media’s autonomy and independence would be strengthened, establish professional journalist responsibility and ethics and maintain social stability.

The long-term development policy of Mongolia, “Vision-2050,” was approved by the Parliament of Mongolia on May 13, 2020, and the implementation of the policy in 2021-2030 includes:

- Freedom of the press will be ensured in all aspects, and ethical and professional journalism will be developed

- Enlightenment activities of the masses will be reflected in education programs at all levels by the lifestyle, culture and behavior of Mongolians, implemented through the media, and a justice system will be formed.

- Regularly share information about promoting environmental laws and traditional customs of nature conservation through the media and make sure that citizens are involved in nature conservation activities. To develop cultured citizens of the city, a project involving all levels of educational institutions will be implemented and social impact activities will be implemented in the activities of government organizations and mass media. (www.legalinfo.mn, 2023).

It is a good thing that issues of media freedom, autonomy, independence, professional, ethical journalism and the development of specialized journalism are reflected in Mongolia's National Security concept and the long-term development policy “Vision 2050”. However, it is still unclear how to implement it and what approach to follow. Further, there is still no unified policy and planning for the development of the media industry or measurable goals and objectives, their basic level, achievement results, implementation activities, funding sources, and implementation control indicators set forth by the media industry to achieve progress on specific development issues in the long, medium and short term at the regional and local levels. Additionally, there is no document yet that includes the collective interests that are reflected.

THE CURRENT SITUATION

Journalism in Mongolia is going through a period of change due to competition from new media and a growing interest in professional journalism. According to statistics released by the Mongolian Press Institute on June 30, 2023, by 2022, 188 online media, 115 TV channels, 59 newspapers, 43 magazines, and 46 radio FM radio stations are currently delivering articles and programs to Mongolia's 3.4 million population. Mongolian journalism continues to play an important role in society. In addition to providing access to news and information, they also maintain culture and initiate various programs that meet the interests and demands of consumers.

Chart 2. Growth of Mongolian Media 1999-2022

Source: Mongolian Media Today, Press Institute 2023

According to the research released by the Press Institute, the number of media outlets is decreasing. Among them, the number of newspapers and magazines has been steadily declining in recent years and has reached its lowest level in the 24 years since the survey began. The number of television stations, which has been stable in recent years, has decreased. (Mongolian

Press institute, 2023) Currently, 188 news sites in Mongolia regularly distribute current information to the public and the number of local news sites is also growing, according to the research.

Quantitative changes in media outlets

The number of media outlets operating in 2018-2022 in Mongolia

Table 3.

Quantitative changes in media outlets 1999-2022

		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
NEWSPAPERS	Daily	10	9	8	7	6
	Per 3-4 days	4	4	3	3	4
	Weekly	23	22	20	16	16
	Biweekly	37	29	29	25	22
	Monthly	13	15	14	9	8
	Other	5	5	3	4	0
	Total	92	84	78	64	59
MAGAZINES	Weekly	2	2	2	2	1
	Biweekly	4	4	2	0	0
	Monthly	28	27	24	16	13
	Quarterly	6	5	5	3	0
	Other	4	4	9	7	7
	Total	78	73	69	46	43
RADIO STATIONS		50	51	51	50	46
TELEVISION STATIONS		128	140	137	135	115
WEBSITES		109	154	178	191	188
TOTAL MEDIA OUTLETS		457	502	513	486	451

Source: Mongolian Media Today 2023, Press Institute

More than 4,400 people are working in the media industry; half are journalists and editors. Fifty-one percent of all employees work in the television industry, and 54 percent are women.

In Mongolia, 21 reporters and camera operators from 13 publications and news agencies such as Al Jazeera, Xinhua, Renmin Ribiao newspaper, China Central Radio and Television CCTV, Asahi Shimbun, Kyodo Tsushin, Fuji TV, Mongolnow.com, Reuters, including IntelliNews, Agence France Presse, Associated Press and KBS TV are working regularly. They

work as a bridge to broadcast Mongolia's political, economic, historical, cultural traditions, social prosperity and achievements to the world and deliver real-time news. Foreign correspondents' applicants who are planning to be permanent or temporary correspondents and getting Mongolian visa residence permits is decided by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. The Ministry of Foreign Affairs has been paying particular attention to promoting foreign policy, democracy and reform processes internationally, strengthening friendly relations

with the countries of the world, increasing mutual exchange between citizens and closely cooperating with media and information organizations.

As the number of Internet users in Mongolia is increasing rapidly, it is becoming more popular to get information from new media rather than traditional media. Citizens' use of social media is very high and in The Inclusive Internet Index 2023 list issued by Meta, Mongolia is ranked 62nd in the world and fifth out of 22 Asian countries. (index, 2023) According to the list,

the most used social networking platform is Facebook. As of September 2023, there are 2,974,000 users of Instagram, X and Facebook in Mongolia, which is 89.1% of the total population. Considering the gender group, the majority, 53.7%, are women, and 758,900 users are 25-34 years old. There are 1,083,300 users of Instagram, which is 32.5% of the total population. Most of the users are women, and the age group is 18-24 years old. As for X, 131,500 users are using the platform.

Chart 3. Social media users

Source: <https://social-cdn.napoleoncat.com/i/2023/09/>

Mongolians registered on Facebook are 2.9 million out of a total 3.4 million population, but among these users, there are also fake accounts and social bots. Media, government organizations, and business organizations have opened their official pages on Facebook, presenting their activities and sharing information regularly. The number of followers on social platforms is

also becoming more and more valuable and the more followers a given medium has, the more excellent the opportunity to reach more people simultaneously.

Facebook pages with the highest follower count [Mongolia]

Table 4.

Facebook pages with the highest follower count

	Facebook page	Followers
TV stations	Mongol TV	1200000
	EDU TV	1000000
	NTV	860000
	TV5	775000
	MNB	628000
News websites	zarig.mn	1100000
	mass.mn	1100000
	ikon.mn	710000
	gogo.mn	678000
	medee.mn	544000
State organizations	Government of Mongolia	203000
	Office of the President	173000
	Parliamentary office	96000
	Directorate General of Police - Press office	259000
	E-Mongolia (Government e-services)	165000

Source: www.facebook.com

Mongol TV has 1,200,000 followers, which is the page with the most followers among media outlets and the page with the most followers in Mongolia. In recent years, major national projects and international TV shows (Voice of Mongolia, Talented Mongolians, Secret World of Six-Year-Olds, etc.) have been successfully localized and users have followed them in large numbers because they regularly post information and advertisements on their Facebook pages. EDU TV is also famous for its entertainment programs and shows

(Just Like It, National Literacy Champion) and has a social media following of one million users. NTV has 860,000 followers, TV5 has 775,000 followers and Mongolian National Broadcaster has 628,000 followers. Zarig and Mass news sites have the most followers, totaling 1100 thousand users, while ikon.mn has 710 thousand followers, gogo.mn has 678 thousand followers and medee.mn has 544 thousand followers. One new post on their Facebook page can instantly reach more than 1 million users, and if those users share it on

their Facebook page, it will reach many people simultaneously. Compared to news sites, the number of followers following the official pages of TV channels is relatively high. Looking at the number of followers of the 5 most followed TV channels and news sites, the TV station with the highest number of followers has 100 thousand more followers than the most followed news site and the top 5 television stations have 84 thousand more followers than the top 5 news sites. Government organizations and politicians open and develop their official pages and share news and information. As can be seen from the data below, government organizations have a relatively small following compared to the media. The Facebook page of the Media Center of the General Police Department has 259,000 followers, which is the most followed among government institutions. The official page of the Government of Mongolia has 203,000 followers, the official page of the Office of the President has 173,000 followers, the official page of the Great Khural of Mongolia has 96,000 followers, and the Integrated State Service System E-Mongolia has 165,000 followers. Government organizations and mass media organizations deliver their information through their channels while also sharing it on Facebook to deliver it to many people without delay. Since the use of the Internet in Mongolia is high, as well as Facebook among social platforms, all media outlets and organizations are trying to get more followers by opening their official pages.

In the national research report "2021 Basic Survey on Internet Usage of Citizens" financed by the (Commission, 2021), the average time spent using the Internet in one day was 7 hours and 13 minutes, while in the 2020 Television Viewing Survey Report of Maxima Consulting Company, "The average time spent by TV viewers is 5 hours 4 minute" is noted. It can be seen that the user spends more time on the Internet than watching television. (consulting, 2020) Recently, the competition for new media has been increasing due to the introduction of high-end technology and the attraction of many followers on social networks. Rather than waiting for an evening or hourly news program, people are more likely to watch live feeds on Facebook for information. Therefore, interest in quality sources and professional journalism is increasing.

FUTURE TRENDS AND CHALLENGES

Today, the number of mass media in Mongolia is steadily growing, along with Internet journalism, environmental journalism, investigative journalism, mobile journalism, citizen journalism, economic journalism, analytical journalism, cable television and radio stations (New areas of journalism and new journalistic tools are emerging, such as FM). In short, information is no longer governed by either space or time. Therefore, to move from quantity to quality, it is necessary to carry out a clear, targeted and meaningful policy, to take bold steps, and to have professional ethics. According to the results of the "Public Opinion Poll: Residents of Mongolia" (poll, 2022) conducted by the International Institute of Republicans, ordinary citizens expressed their opinions on how social media can influence decision-making activities in Mongolia (29% of respondents in 2021, 27% of respondents in 2022). In addition (69% in 2021 and 62% in 2022), the media has a more positive reputation among the public than other public and non-governmental institutions.

As the media's reputation is relatively positive among the public, there is a need to strengthen it further and adhere to the principles of professional ethics that distinguish the media from social networks. (research, 2019) In international practice, media organizations are adopting unified guidelines for self-regulation when working in the online environment. The above guidelines aim to protect the organization's reputation, prevent misleading citizens and protect journalists and reporters from external risks.

Establishing ethical media

The "Media Council" was established in 2015 on the initiative of journalists, non-governmental organizations and professional organizations in the field of media industry. The organization approved the "Principles of Journalism Ethics", "Ensure that the information is true and avoid making accidental mistakes" and "Check the reliability of the source and strive to mention it". The most common complaints are "Assume unconfirmed information, assumptions, and word of mouth." In sum, this shows that journalists and editors are not adequately fulfilling their primary duties of confirming and verifying information and preparing information with sources. (report, 2022).

Chart 4. Complaints from citizens to the Media Council (2012-2022) (2012-2022)

Source: Media Council report 2022 www.mediacouncil.mn

Many international and domestic studies have shown that the media industry has failed to stabilize significantly due to the polarization of editorial policy and the loss of norms, even though Mongolia has almost 30 years since the transition to the free media sector. (J.Batzul, 2022)

To develop an ethical press, it is necessary to establish the independence of the editors and the related regulations in detail. In Mongolia, information about media and the interests of their owners is not officially published and disclosed and only some of the data can be obtained by actively searching and researching. Communications Regulatory Commission policy requires media owners and management to be revealed, but there is no provision for public disclosure of their interests, such as family members or political party affiliations. (Mongolia M. o., 2016) Therefore, there is a need for a policy to openly announce the ownership of

the media and ensure that the owner does not influence the internal policy of the editorial office.

Media ownership is still not open to the public. Information about media and their owners' political and business affiliations can only be found through research. According to the latest study by the Mongolian Press Institute, most media (74%) are privately owned. This study applies to all media types, but the television industry has more privately owned press than any other industry. On the other hand, the magazine industry is owned mainly by NGOs. Many media outlets claim to be private but are affiliated with large business groups and politicians, and there is no legal regulation to disclose the real owners and investors. It is not denied that the media does not introduce unfavorable information about its owners, investors or information that harms their interests.

Chart 5. Ownership of Media outlets

Source: Mongolian Media Today, Press Institute 2023

People prefer news and information from reliable sources. However, due to no supervision on Facebook, some people mislead the the public by deliberately spreading false information. Unfortunately, fact-checking has not yet been developed in Mongolia, leading to misleading people with incorrect information and distrust in statement. Therefore, the problem of being a responsible and reliable source, verifying the data and delivering it to the public is still a pressing problem in journalism. Journalist ethics is important to combat false, fake, and misleading information. News organizations are investing in fact-checking initiatives and developing tools to combat the spread of incorrect information online. www.factchek.mn, the first independent and professional non-profit editorial office in the media sector of Mongolia, was established by the non-governmental organization "Investigative Journalism" and is affiliated with the non-governmental organization serving society "Journalism Innovation and Development Center" under the jurisdiction of "Mongolian Fact" - Checking Center" www.mfcc.mn works to verify the information broadcasted in the online environment and deliver true and correct information to the public. Also, the National Center for Comprehensive Development, a non-governmental organization, operates

www.uih.mn, an independent non-profit site aimed at improving representation responsibility and supporting citizen control, and conducts Fact-checking on information provided by members of Parliament and the Office of the Parliament. For them, they perform Factcheck on the information published on the official website of the Office of the Parliament, all kinds of information given by the members of the Parliament during the session and to the press, as well as the information shared by the members of the Parliament on their personal Facebook.

Strengthening professional, ethical, autonomous, and independent media is essential for fighting fake and misleading news. Therefore, if editors clarify their policies and maintain ethical standards, the public will ignore false information from unverified sources and only trust verified sources.

In the XXII Report "State of Human Rights and Freedoms in Mongolia," released by the National Human Rights Commission in 2023, the issue of freedom of the press was considered, and suggestions on improving were submitted to Parliament. Although there is freedom of the press, there are still economic and political impacts, such as non-transparency of media ownership, lack of funding and journalists' salaries and

workload. It was considered necessary to improve the legal framework to strengthen autonomy. (Mongolia N. H., 2023)

Developing media management

At a time when social media has become a significant source of information for people, it is important to understand and increase the value of journalism, as well as to develop media as a business model and improve management. Talking about "media independence" without sustainable financial operations is pointless. Media business information is not openly accessible to the public. On the other hand, the owners see the publishing business as a means of protecting their political position and economic interests rather than making a profit.

Maxima Consulting LLC, an independent research organization, presented the current state of the Mongolian media market in 2019. According to the report, international commercial television revenues are advertising 85-90% (sponsorship 2%), content sales 10-15% and large project investment. But in Mongolia Advertising 50% (including barter 20%), Sponsorship 15%, 10% paid and subscription news programs, 7% of content sales, Subsidy of owners, other hidden sources 18%.

In addition, the organization has published a comprehensive report on television viewer ratings in Mongolia since 2014 and a list of the top 20 advertising suppliers in the television market. In 2014, the Government of Mongolia was ranked 19th in terms of payment for the payment of overall total advertisement income. Since 2018, the government has been leading in advertisement payments. It can be seen that one of the main contributors to advertising in this industry is the government. In the City Capital budget of 2023, the Capital Governor's Office has a budget of 650 million MNT or about 208 thousand US dollars for media expenses. (<http://shd.mn/mn/images/shd/upload/2023-niisleltosov-15-togtool.pdf>, 2022) The Media Institute provides training and consulting services for media business models and digital transitions. A researcher at the institute, J. Oyuntsetseg, noted various opportunities for earning media business through paid content, the traditional income generation model, donation, subscription, crowdfunding and social paywall.

To develop media industry management, there is an opportunity to increase capacity and raise funds by participating in external projects and programs in addition to internal sources. To localize a sustainable and independent business model in the media industry; the "Walk Forward" project was implemented by the Journalism Innovation and Development Center with the support of the US Embassy in Mongolia. Within the framework of the project, four start-ups were born in the media sector with the help of 100 million MNT. Since foreign investment is prohibited in the media industry by law, steps are being taken to attract domestic investment. Specifically, the first public joint-stock company in the media sector was established in April 2022, and its shares are traded openly through the Mongolian Stock Exchange. "Tengerlig Media Group" JSC is the first joint-stock company in the media industry in Mongolia; initial public offering on the Mongolian

Stock Exchange with a total number of shares of 6 million, and the current exchange rate (as of October 18, 2023) is 7700 MNT or about 2 US dollars. 10% of the total shares were allocated to the group's employees. This strategy sets a new standard for other media organizations. Because shares are owned by many investors and shareholders, it is independent of one owner, reduces the interference of owners and politicians in editorial policies, and allows the public to own the media company, control its operations and benefit from profits and returns.

The primary income of media organizations is from government and business organizations' advertisements. Additionally, it is supplemented by donations, subscriptions, content payments and paid services. It is still unclear how much the market capacity of the media sector can be expressed in monetary terms. "Eguur" news agency reported on May 3, 2021, that there is an estimate that the combined amount is about 50 billion MNT and an average of 17 million US dollars. (eguur.mn, 2022) but this is a rough figure, and media agencies' funding and revenue information remain confidential. Therefore, there is a need to introduce new business models and increase income sources in this sector.

Regulating the relationship between government organizations and media

Although it is forbidden by law for a state organization to have media under its control, the media office under the state organization has become too complicated and has a cumbersome structure. It operates at the level of a news agency. Since then, press offices have produced content, uploaded it to social networks independently and distributed it to other media outlets. As a result, the media are only distributors and transmitters of the content submitted by the Press Office. For example, the Press Office of the Government has expanded into the Department of Media and Public Relations and operates with 18 employees, including the Speech Department, Electronic Information Department, Newspaper Publishing Department, Content Development Department and Foreign Information Promotion Department. However, the editors of the leading news sites in Mongolia: news.mn 30, gogo.mn 15, ikon.mn 16, zarig.mn 24, ergelt.mn 18, itoim.mn 8 employees regularly operate as enterprises.

The Bank of Mongolia, through its "Regulations on Media and Public Relations", regulates how to publish paid advertisements, articles, translations, and interviews in the press and media and selects media organizations and journalists who have worked diligently to convey the Bank of Mongolia's policy to the public accurately and encourages transparency. Only one such organization has approved its media relations policy and how its press department and journalists will work together.

One of the important issues in the development of journalism in Mongolia is the adoption of a legal act to regulate the relationship between the state, media owners, legal entities and individuals and to create regulations on how the press office under the government organization should work, taking into account the experience of developed countries and international standards

is in demand. In addition, it is important to control illegal information that misleads, discriminates and degrades morals.

Introduction of new technologies

A sign of significant changes in the media industry is using new technologies such as virtual reality and artificial intelligence in journalism. MNB introduced its first virtual presenter to the public in September 2023, a first for the television industry. In the future, it is expected to continue to develop in line with technological progress. As online media plays an increasingly important role in social life, it is only natural that there is a need to use new technologies to create more interactive and extensive content. Virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) technologies are changing how we consume media. It is unique in that it offers users new content with digital content and allows them to interact as if they were in the environment. Media outlets are successfully using innovations in social platforms in their operations. For example, live streaming platforms have grown in popularity, allowing individuals and organizations to broadcast real-time video content to a global audience. This technology has revolutionized how we share events, news and entertainment, making it possible for anyone to stream live from anywhere.

Media organizations are starting to use artificial intelligence and AI in news writing and editing, content creation, personalization and recommendation systems. AI algorithms can understand user preferences, analyze large amounts of data to deliver tailored content, and have the advantage of contextualizing a wide range of content quickly.

The 5G network has recently been introduced in Mongolia and it is expected to be introduced rapidly in the future. 5G networks enable faster and more reliable internet connections, enabling seamless streaming of high-quality media content on mobile devices. This technology is a new opportunity for media consumption and distribution. Understanding how to optimally use big data, develop online and offline subscriptions and introduce advertising automation and content management is important.

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

Mongolian national journalism has a history spanning more than 110 years. On March 6, 1913, the newspaper "Shine toli hemeeh bichig" was published, and in 1934, the Mongolian National Radio began broadcasting articles, and in 1967, the Mongolian National Television began broadcasting. Thus, Mongolia's media system was believed to be created in the 1970s. Over 110 years of development, Mongolian journalism has overcome socio-economic challenges and has been enriched by contemporary requirements and scientific and technological achievements. Periodicals, radio, television and news agencies are developing in their way and are still going through development and transition.

Democracy and pluralism have taken a central place in the media, news, articles, and broadcasts, which has brought significant changes to Mongolian journalism, and a new style has emerged in journalism

that has never existed before. Today, Mongolian journalism is one of the strongest social and political institutions. They have become a powerful platform for shaping public opinion, criticizing negative phenomena, restoring truth and justice, blowing the whistle on corruption, and contributing significantly to people's ability to think and act in new ways. On the other hand, there is a real need for journalism to become more professional, to use the scientific and technological achievements of humanity and to distinguish professional journalism from civilian journalism.

One of the pressing problems is the lack of a comprehensive policy and concept for developing the media industry in Mongolia. How should the media industry develop, what procedures should be used to create independent, autonomous and professional journalism, and what criteria should be reached in the long and short-term view and adjust your arrangements?

In addition, the public must monitor the activities of the government, state organizations, and authorized officials to provide information to the public, improve transparency, and actively perform the role of monitoring the implementation of the law. It is necessary to comprehensively consider the issue of self-regulation of the media, to strengthen the independence of the editors, including the strengthening of the independent media regulatory bodies and to improve the financial freedom of the press. Therefore, it is necessary to refine the legal framework further, revise regulations governing many unsolved issues and approve legal laws governing many new relationships that will emerge in the rapidly developing new media era. Therefore, it is necessary to refine the legal framework further, revise regulations governing many unsolved issues and approve legal laws governing many new relationships that will emerge in the rapidly developing new media era.

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